

README

All files are gathered in `dataset_and_scripts.zip`.

All scripts are written for python 3.7.7. Required python packages are:

- `sys`, `os`, `numpy` (1.21.6), `pandas` (1.3.5), `matplotlib` (3.51), `scipy` (1.7.3), `json`, `mpl_toolkits`, `math`, `glob`
- `core_tools` version 1.4.6 (https://github.com/stephanphilips/core_tools)

Figures can be created by opening `paper_figures_script.py` (e.g. in Spyder) and executing it cell by cell. Except of the first two cells each cell generates a specific figure of the work.

Raw data is located in the folder `raw_data`, `descriptons` of the raw data can be found in `data_overview_sheets`. Pre-processed data is located in `conflated_data`. If it is deleted the corresponding figure code will generate it again automatically.